

STRESS AND TEMPERATURE INDUCED DAMAGE
IN SOLID ROCKET MOTOR CASES

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Present design and analysis of filament-wound solid rocket motor cases is firmly entrenched in the use of linear, orthotropic elastic analysis coupled with the application of "experience factors" to account for effects such as temperature, case layup geometry, hydrotesting, etc. Glass/epoxy filament-wound composites are used extensively in motor cases as the primary pressure vessel. Typically the motor environments range from 20 to 120°F and cover a variety of mechanical and thermal loads during storage or operational conditions, the motor case is initially subjected to a hydrotest proof cycle to pressure levels about 10 to 25 percent above the expected operating conditions.

Both of these loading situations are particularly severe in the dome regions where the fiber angles are high ($> 45^\circ$) and considerable internal damage is created within the composite material. This type of damage results from a combination of matrix viscoelastic behavior and internal crack growth. The damage, in the form of microcrack growth and crazing, is shown by experiment to be a function of applied stress level, fiber angle and layup geometry, number of imposed cycles, stress field, and temperature. Using unidirectional and laminated (angle-ply) samples from molded glass/epoxy plates, the induced damage is evaluated in terms of the load-temperature history. The effects of creep stress in tensile and bending fields are evaluated against constant strain rate environments in similar stress fields. The results of the molded plate samples are then compared with tests conducted on samples removed from the dome area of an operational solid rocket motor case. Again, both creep and constant strain rate tests were conducted for multiple cycles.

Multiple cycling effects were found to be more sensitive to the effective stress normal to the fibers than to the shear stress. The Lebesgue norm was found to approximately characterize these types of cumulative damage in highly filled particulate solid propellants under similar loading histories. The higher order Lebesgue (L_8 or higher) norms were typically used for propellant behavior. The second-order Lebesgue (L_2) norm was found to approximately characterize the glass/epoxy damage effects. The L_2 norm which, at a given time, is proportional to the root-mean-square (RMS) value of the stress is found to represent the type of damage induced by hydrotest (multiple stress cycles) and thermal loads.